

BUILDING RESILIENCE FROM VIOLENT EXTREMISM THROUGH DEVELOPMENT OF SECURITY CULTURE

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Abstract

Resilience is the ability of a person to mentally and emotionally cope with a crisis and to be able to return to the pre-crisis state, while using mental processes and behaviours to promote personal resources and protect themselves from the negative effects that it can cause. The development of mental and behavioural abilities, according to this definition, enables individuals to cope with the newly emerging situation, to overcome the crisis and to be able to cope with further negative consequences.

In building resilience to the emergence of violent extremism, understanding the reasons for its emergence, i.e. the initiator of radical and even extremist behaviour, is essential. There is no exact profile of a person who is ready to commit extreme violence, but people become terrorists in different ways, in different roles and for different reasons. The process of radicalization can be initiated or fuelled by socio-political or socio-psychological circumstances that directly or indirectly affect the individual. The reasons why individuals join radicalized groups, as well as the reasons why such groups are formed, are complex, diverse and, above all, of a local nature. Therefore, we believe that the development of a security culture at the local, national and regional levels is extremely important for creating predispositions for resilience to extremism, violent extremism and terrorism.

Keywords: resilience, violent extremism, security culture

Defining the concept of security culture

The phenomenon of culture, as a social phenomenon, is the subject of study by philosophy, science and religion, however, a universal definition has not yet been established. Some researchers mention several hundred different definitions. By the concept of *culture*, we mean many different phenomena in society. It represents the totality of human creativity and is divided into material and spiritual culture. This gives us the right to speak more about culture descriptively than to try to define it, without being able to fully explain it.

In everyday speech, the concept of culture refers to the creative activity of people (the arts) as well as to the habits, customs, and lifestyle of people or groups that are highly valued in society. Raymond Williams, who is considered one of the most important theorists of culture, explains the concept of culture with the following definition: Everything that man has created or produced from nature is culture, and everything that

exists or arises without human participation, without human "interference", is nature or part of nature⁴⁴.

Every culture forms its own symbols, which facilitate communication. Symbols are: words, numbers, drawings, photographs, parts of clothing, hairstyles, gestures, signs. In addition to the visible components of culture, it also contains invisible components, which are the values and specific rules of behaviour (norms) that guide and regulate human behaviour.

Fig. 1. Source: Santa Claus Culture Model⁴⁵

Society could not exist without rules (norms) or standards for “appropriate” behaviour. Norms in society are expressed through: laws, customs and moral rules. The most important norms in society are institutionalized in appropriate institutions. For society to function, there must be ways to strengthen norms, and these are sanctions.

Values are ideas about what is good, right, wise, useful. They represent the highest criteria from which norms are derived. Values are those things and ideas that are important to us and in which we believe. Knowledge, that is, ideas and information, are also an integral part of culture.

Security should be seen as a broad concept: in addition to avoiding previous undesirable events, the focus should be on new potential risks. Focusing exclusively on certain risks or practices, other relevant issues are often neglected. Security is a physical and psychological need of people, but security cannot be directly monitored, although people can directly monitor dangers, risks, accidents, disasters, losses, injuries, etc⁴⁶.

Security culture, from a modern perspective, refers to the way in which certain ideas about the security order and structures are developed, as well as what we have perceived as a danger to our lives or threats to our values, and at the same time it is our

⁴⁴ Слободнка Ристевска, Алберт Хани и група автори: Социјални вештини- Скопје ОБСЕ 2001, стр, 133

⁴⁵ http://eurolog-project.eu/pdf/vortrag_gemeinhardt_deutsch.pdf

⁴⁶ http://sr.swewe.net/word_show.htm

most obvious defence against them. Security culture participates in the formation of what is valuable to us. It regulates our moral, economic and political priorities. Security control also sets the limits and possibilities for declaring what is important, valuable or not valuable, what deserves protection or not.

Security culture is a set of beliefs, values and practices of individuals and organizations, which decide what can be seen as a danger and by what means they should be met⁴⁷. In fact, it is a set of adopted attitudes, knowledge, skills and rules in the field of security expressed as ways of behaviour and means of protecting personal, social and international values from all kinds of threats.

Security culture is understood as a security activity that expresses readiness to act and behave in accordance with the acquired knowledge and skills, as well as in accordance with the accepted attitudes about values. It is reflected in the recognition of dangers, reacting to them by avoiding dangers, averting dangers or by referring to those subjects who will professionally react and preserve the threatened values.

According to Alastair Ian Johnstone, security culture can be defined as "an integrated system of symbols that underpin long-term strategic performance by formulating concepts about the role and effectiveness of military forces in international relations, presenting these strategic performances as so factual that they seem unambiguously realistic and efficient"⁴⁸.

Security culture is part of the political culture of a community's politics. Since the creation of modern nation-states, it has become clear that cultures can be shaped by constructs and conscious policies, but they can also be a tool and help shape people's awareness of their biases, emotions, patterns of behaviour, and political preferences. Unlike political, strategic, and organizational culture, security culture requires the establishment of norms and rules of behaviour in security, in a system as a whole, in its individual components, and at the key points of security initiatives and decisions at the level of the state or another entity.

The culture and rules of behaviour in security change, develop, and become more complex in accordance with the changed role of the state and with the change in the security space/ambience within the state or outside the state space/territory.

In this context, we can conclude that since the moment when the term "security culture" first appeared, the frequency of use of the term has expanded significantly, especially in the media, and then in literature⁴⁹. From the very emergence of the term to the present day, its use has almost doubled. This process involves the separation of the concept from its original context and the emergence of new meanings and references.

In man as part of the general culture, security culture is best assessed and valued according to one's attitude towards the values that are a condition for human life and for the development of society. At the current moment in which Macedonian society finds itself, security culture has not yet been created and shaped as a separate form of consciousness, because it is a long and complex process in which changes need to be made in people's consciousness in terms of the new value system, defined in the Constitution of

⁴⁷ Forschung für die zivile Sicherheit 2012 – 2017 Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) http://www.bmbf.de/pub/rahmenprogramm_sicherheitsforschung_2012.pdf

⁴⁸ Стајић, Љубомир С., Мијалковић, Саша и Станаревић, Светлана. Безбедносна култура младих: како живети безбедно, Београд: Драганић, 2006. Johnston, Alastair И. "Thinking about strategic culture", International Security, Вол.19, но. 4, (1995) Katzenstein, Peter J., ed. Culture of National Security, New York: Columbia University Press, 1996.

⁴⁹ The term "safety culture" first appeared in 1986, with the Chernobyl nuclear disaster.

the Republic of Macedonia. But, despite this, we will try to explain this concept in a general and descriptive way: "Security culture is part of the general culture of man as an individual, of people in a certain environment and space, or of society as a whole. The content of security culture is a special form of consciousness that is expressed as a set of progressive tendencies and knowledge in the field of security that make the bearer of security culture (man) capable of recognizing the basic values and benefits of civilization; the dangers of threats to those values, goods and benefits and the need for them to be successfully protected and promoted"⁵⁰.

Security culture from a modern point of view refers to the way in which certain ideas about the security order and structures are developed, as well as what we have noticed as a danger to life or a threat to our values, and it is also our most obvious defence against them. It participates in the formation of what is valuable to us. It regulates our moral, economic and political priorities. It also sets limits and opportunities to declare what is important, valuable or not valuable, what is worth protecting or not. Security culture is a set of beliefs, perceptions and attitudes that reflect the importance that individuals in the organization contribute to security, for themselves on a personal level, as well as for the safety of others. Security culture is developed, created, and nurtured most often through socialization processes.

Manifestations of security culture

In the context of the given definition that security culture is a set of adopted attitudes, knowledge, skills and rules in the field of security, it can be concluded that it manifests itself as a behaviour and a process, for the needs, ways and means of protecting personal, social and international values from all sources, forms and carriers of threat, regardless of the place or time of their manifestation. Security culture has its internal and external manifestations⁵¹:

- Internal manifestations refer to the consideration of security,
- External manifestations are the behaviour in security, as well as the attitude and approach to security, which primarily refers to the readiness and ability, whether material or spiritual, to respond to challenges and threats.

It is known that attitudes are permanent systems of positive or negative assessments, emotional categories and techniques for the pros and cons of activities in a community. Attitudes, as part of the security culture, represent a set of beliefs about situations or issues in life that are shared by members of a society or community that has a predisposition to be related to these issues or in those situations in which they should behave in a certain way.

Strengthening non-governmental and civil society organizations is perhaps one of the most important aspects for the development of security culture⁵².

⁵⁰ Спасески Јордан, Столб на безбедноста и мирот на Балканот, Академик, Скопје, 2005

⁵¹ Стајић, Љ.; Мијалковић, С.; Станаревић, С. (2013). Безбедносна култура. Нови Сад: Правни факултет Универзитета у Новом Саду.

⁵² С. Станаревиќ : Концепт за безбедносната култура и претпоставки за нејзиниот развој , докторска дисертација Београд, 2012.

Resilience

Mental resilience refers to an individual's ability to recover from extreme trauma and stress, and represents a set of factors that promote positive adaptation despite exposure to adverse life experiences. These factors include individual protective factors, such as a positive personal outlook, family protective factors, which refer to support from family members, and social protective factors, among which the individual's social integration is particularly important⁵³. All of these factors can contribute to an individual's ability to cope more easily with negative life events, which leads to increased self-esteem, self-confidence, and a sense of well-being.

Resilience is the ability of an individual to mentally and emotionally cope with a crisis and to be able to return to the pre-crisis state, using mental processes and behaviours to enhance personal resources and protect against the negative effects that certain situations can cause⁵⁴. The development of mental and behavioural abilities, according to this definition, allows individuals to cope with the newly emerging situation, overcome the crisis, and face further negative consequences.

Psychological resilience refers to the capacity of an individual to withstand stressors without manifesting psychological dysfunction, such as mental illness or persistent negative mood, i.e. it is defined as the ability of a person to avoid psychopathological phenomena despite difficult circumstances. Psychological resilience is the ability and skill of an individual to see their problems as a challenge and an opportunity for personal growth and development⁵⁵.

The term resilience refers to the "ability to recover" from something that is experienced as stress or threat. The original definition of resilience was given by Murray and Zautra, who listed three processes or aspects that constitute the adaptive response to challenging situations⁵⁶:

- Recovery – suggests that the person is able to make necessary psychophysiological and social adjustments and return to the level of functioning that existed before the stressful situation.
- Sustainability – people can experience a slight decline in functioning, but continue to move forward, towards personal goals and objectives that make their lives meaningful, with minimal impact of stressors on their health and well-being. Sustainability testifies to the ability of the individual to thrive despite misfortunes and stressful events.
- Growth – includes additional benefits and progress after the misfortune, primarily through new knowledge, acquisition of new skills, strengthening of self-confidence, achieving a new life perspective and a stronger sense of self.

⁵³ Ahern, Kiehl, Sole, Byers, A methodological review of resilience measurement scales. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 2009

⁵⁴ Robertson, Kuper, Sarkar и Curran "The Same Staff Can Be Enough". *Employers' Resilience Strategies in Recruitment Decisions*, 2015

⁵⁵ Affleck & Tennen, Ryff et al.,, The Structure of Psychological Well-Being Revisited., - *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 2012

⁵⁶ Murray & Zautra, *Resilience: A new definition of health for people and communities*, 2008

Violent extremism

Violent extremism is a dynamic process in which an extremist individual accepts violence as a possible, and even legitimate, way of acting in order to achieve their own goals. Their own goals can be a reflection of the collective thinking of a certain group of people, nation, religious denomination, party organization or other type of organization or they can be a reflection of their own thinking and actions. This means that violent extremism can be exposed through an individually or collectively organized way of understanding and interpreting the situations and positioning in terms of responding to the situations themselves (social, economic, military, social). Such actions are aimed at:

- Readiness to support far-reaching changes in society, which can aim at abolishing the established democratic legal order and can include the use of undemocratic methods;
- A process that leads an individual or group to accept, support or encourage the use of violence as a political tool;
- A process of personal development in which the individual adopts increasingly extreme political or political-religious ideas and goals, convincing themselves that achieving these goals justifies the use of violent extreme methods.

Indicators of radicalization leading to violent extremism

The main indicators for recognizing the radicalization process are: identity, ideology and behaviour. Other indicators are:

- Changing names – using pseudonyms (which sometimes refer to their ideological role models);
- Changing the style of clothing, usually using a certain fashion brand;
- Changing physical appearance, such as shaving or growing hair/beard;
- Tattoos (hidden), badges or symbols;
- Seeking or having frequent contact with leaders of radical groups;
- Possession of propaganda materials – pamphlets, books, DVDs;
- Changes in religious practices;
- Participation in private meetings (living room meetings);
- Use of the Internet for specific purposes (e.g. social networks or chat rooms with radical content);
- Glorification of martyrdom or violence;
- Change in travel patterns or residence in certain areas (e.g. conflict zones, foreign fighters);
- Open expression of extremist views (e.g. participation in radical demonstrations, listening to radical music groups);
- Isolation from society and association with new peers and groups, i.e. staying away from school and youth clubs;
- Change in attitudes when interacting with other people – use of radical or specific terminology;
- Committing minor crimes in order to show disrespect for the Government or society.

Understanding the reasons why certain individuals are willing to give their lives to a violent extremist movement or cause and the actions being taken to address and alleviate the problems and grievances that push them to take such an extremist course represent an important investment of our time and resources.

Causes of radicalization include:

- strong post-traumatic and "fictive kinship" identifications with Sunni Muslims who are under attack as people in the region have also recently suffered the same;
- humanitarian concerns and altruistic motives;
- high unemployment;
- material benefits from joining;
- the desire for personal significance;
- calls for jihad and apocalyptic end-of-times thinking;
- the desire to build and live in an Islamic "Caliphate" and according to Sharia law; and
- the desire and need to keep family ties intact when a family member is convinced to go to Syria⁵⁷, etc.

Building resilience among radicalized individuals who exhibit violent extremism, through developing a culture of safety

Studying the reasons, motives and goals of radicalized individuals who readily adopt violent methods of expressing their extremism, in order to achieve certain goals, helps us to adequately address the problem and determine the most appropriate measures and actions to counter them. Resilience itself can be built in the form of preventive activities, expressed through various forms and methods. This involves taking proactive actions to counter the efforts of violent extremists that they make in the direction of radicalizing, recruiting and mobilizing followers to commit violence, as well as to deal with certain factors that facilitate the recruitment of violent extremists and the process of radicalization towards violence. In this sense, radicalization is not understood as a linear process that goes through precisely defined phases at a constant pace, i.e. speed, but rather it is a variable that is conditioned by the local context and individual factors. :

-The application of complex educational, economic and security measures and activities aimed at raising public awareness and resistance to the motivating factors and tools that encourage radicalization and violent extremism;

-Development and implementation of projects to build awareness of the dangers of extremism and violent extremism;

-Taking measures to prevent radicalization in schools, cultural institutions and prisons;

-Raising awareness among citizens and the private sector in the fight against violent extremism that can lead to terrorism and promoting tolerance and public understanding of all types of dangers of violent extremism and terrorism.

Such a commitment includes a consensual recognition of the "important roles that youth, families, women, victims of terrorism, religious leaders, cultural and educational leaders, civil society and the media can play in countering violent extremist narratives that can lead to incitement of certain extremists to use violent means to become terrorist actors and carry out terrorist acts, and they, as positive factors, can also influence the resolution

⁵⁷ Улогата на Граѓанското Општество во Спречување и Спротивставување на Насилен Екстремизам и Радикализацијакои Водат кон Тероризам., Водич за Југоисточна Европа, ОБСЕ 2018 година

of those problems that can potentially constitute a basis for the spread of radicalization, violent extremist ideology and terrorism, in particular by fostering mutual respect and understanding, reconciliation and peaceful coexistence between cultures, as well as by promoting and protecting human rights, fundamental freedoms, democratic principles and the rule of law.”

The second step is to apply resocialization and deradicalization methods to those who are already radicalized, who advocate and practice extremism and violent forms of its expression, and who cannot be addressed by preventive activities⁵⁸. Resocialization can be described as “a deliberate, planned intervention that aims to change the characteristics of the offender (attitudes, cognitive skills and processes, personal or mental health, and social, educational or vocational skills) that are believed to be the cause of the individual's criminal behaviour, with the intention of reducing the chances that the individual will reoffend”.

Resocialization and reintegration programmes involve both a cognitive element (changing beliefs and attitudes, often referred to as de-radicalization) and a behavioural element (ceasing violent activities, often referred to as disengagement). Individuals who disengage (disengaged) may have abandoned the path of violence, but still retain their beliefs. Resocialization programmes aim to facilitate the individual's transition back into society⁵⁹.

Rehabilitation programmes target individuals who have been radicalized to violence at various stages of radicalization, and the same may apply to their families. Such types of programmes as prison-based de-radicalization/disengagement programmes, as well as post-crime care programmes that focus on the rehabilitation and reintegration of perpetrators of terrorist activities, as well as the return of foreign fighters and their reintegration into society. Some programmes provide educational and vocational training, counselling, employment opportunities, and ideological re-education, etc.

Some of them, after reaching a certain level, will leave and reintegrate into society, while others will continue the process of radicalization. Those who go through the entire process are likely to be involved in violent extremist or terrorist activities⁶⁰.

⁵⁸ <https://religija.mk/verskite-lideri-se-kluchni-za-spravuvanje-so-ekstremizmot>

⁵⁹ Спречување на радикализацијата и изразувањето на омраза на терен, Насоки за локалните и регионалните власти, Конгрес на локалните и регионални власти на Советот на Европа, март 2016 година

⁶⁰ ОБСЕ МС.ДОС/4/15 (4 декември 2015 година)

CONCLUSION

In addition to the key civil society actors described above, other important factors include educators/teachers, law enforcement agencies, academics/researchers, former violent extremists, the information technology and social media sector, journalists, and media specialists. Also, it is important to recognize that the influence of counterproductive community actors and formal or informal grassroots organizations can negatively impact the agenda for preventing and countering violent extremism and radicalization leading to terrorism.

- It is necessary to conduct continuous joint training for members of the security agencies for prevention and suppression at the regional (primarily with neighbouring countries) and international level, in order to harmonize actions, develop the highest level of cooperation, share information and exchange of experiences, as well as build mutual trust.
- In the same direction, it is necessary to continue and improve inter-institutional cooperation within the countries themselves through the exchange and sharing of good practices and experiences.
- Strengthening and improving the capacities and resources of local prevention councils, advisory civic groups and religious communities in order to undertake specific measures and activities to prevent violent extremism and radicalization of individuals and groups.
- Preparation of a sociological profile by all involved institutions at the national level in order to determine the motive and background for committing terrorist acts.
- More active involvement and engagement of youth and youth associations, families, women, religious, cultural and educational leaders and civil society in addressing the conditions conducive to the spread of violent extremism.
- Designing instruments for assessing the risk of returned foreign fighters and accompanying family members and monitoring their behaviour, lifestyle, relationships and contacts, with increased attention to child returnees from conflict regions.
- Emphasizing the need to establish a special department or body in prisons for intelligence and analysis of information on entities, persons, resources and capacities involved in the process of radicalization and the spread of extremist ideology.
- Examining the situation and possibilities for developing an appropriate programme for rehabilitation, resocialization and reintegration for foreign fighters - returnees, while in prison and afterwards, led by government institutions and in cooperation with partners from civil society, the academic community and of course experts in the field.

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